

GREEN ERA-HUB
on Agri-Food and Biotechnology

Staying on track and Paving the road

D2.1 Integrated Roadmap

Green ERA-Hub

The Green ERA-Hub (GEH) brought together networks in the Agri-food and biotechnology sector including all relevant ERA-Nets (Cofunds), and their predecessors, self-sustained networks and EJP. By this the GEH represented most of the relevant national funders in Europe in the Agri-food and biotechnology sectors. The goal of the GEH was to maintain the momentum and experience gained over the last 18 years of transnational research programming and to use the experience to:

- i.) continue to build on previous achievements and further enhance cross-sector collaborations between Agri-Food and Biotechnology ERA-Nets, through implementation of new joint calls resulting in the funding of transnational collaborative projects;
- ii.) continue valorisation and implementation of other joint activities supporting the market, regulatory or societal uptake of results after the end of individual ERA-Nets;
- iii.) identify common research and innovation priorities, agreed upon by the participating national programmes, and address them via new joint calls;
- iv.) preserve best practice and managerial competences;
- v.) contribute to the planning and complement the implementation of the new HEU Partnerships and Missions;
- vi.) broaden the actions and impact of initiatives towards stakeholders and in terms of geographical coverage;
- vii.) contribute to achieve the strategic goals of the SDGs, in particular zero hunger, industry innovation and infrastructure, responsible consumption and production, life on land, partnership for the goals, the farm2fork strategy and EU's Green Deal.

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Contents

Executive Summary	4
GENERAL OUTLINE AND INTRODUCTION	7
STAYING ON TRACK.....	9
2.1 Networks overview	10
2.2 BIOEAST	12
2.3 CORE ORGANIC	14
2.4 EJP SOIL.....	15
2.5 ERA CAPS	15
2.6 ERA COBIOTECH.....	16
2.7 FACCE ERA-GAS.....	17
2.8 EUPHRESCO	17
2.9 FOSC.....	17
2.10 ICRAD	18
2.11 ICT AGRI FOOD.....	18
2.12 LEAP AGRI	18
2.13 FACCE SURPLUS	18
2.14 SUSAN	19
2.15 SUSCROP	20
2.16 SUSFOOD	21
2.17 FACCE JPI	21
2.18 RESEARCHER INPUT	22
PAVING THE ROAD.....	24
3.1 Learnings from CSA coordination	25
3.2 Learnings from organizing the GEH calls.....	26
3.3 Learnings from the Socratic Dialogue Events.....	28
3.4 Learnings from Monitoring Evaluation and Impact Assessment.....	29
3.5 Learnings on Impact.....	31
3.6 Learnings from the Living Archive	34
3.7 Learnings on Widening	35
3.8 Learnings on the support of Early Career Researchers	37
3.9 Learnings from Communication and Dissemination	38

3.10 Learnings provided by project researchers.....	40
APPENDICES.....	43
Appendix I; Proposed framework for societal impact.....	44

Executive Summary

The Green ERA-Hub (GEH) brings together fifteen European research networks, including ERA-Nets, a European Joint Programme (EJP), and a self-sustained initiative in the fields of agriculture, food, and biotechnology. These networks have built more than two decades of experience in joint programming. The Green ERA-Hub has reached the end of its project after a runtime of four years. During this period, the European research and innovation landscape has changed considerably with the launch of the Horizon Europe Partnerships and the ending of the ERA-Nets.

This report reflects on the continuity of the thematic research areas of the GEH networks, and on the practical experience gained through many years of joint programming. The document therefore consists of two parts. **Part 1, “Staying on Track”** reviews how well the thematic areas of the fifteen GEH networks are currently covered within the European funding landscape.

The assessment shows that many of the topics covered by the GEH networks continue to be addressed through the European Partnerships. However, the analysis also shows that several topics are only partially covered and that several topics are completely missing. The most important topics that are insufficiently addressed are:

- Mitigation, adaptation and resilience to the effects of climate change on food systems from farm to fork;
- Addressing the integrated soil–freshwater–food systems–biomanufacturing nexus;
- Research funding of lower TRLs in the area of biotechnology and its platform technologies;
- Effective trans-national (AU-EU), research, innovation and collaboration on joint challenges in agri, food and climate;
- Molecular plant science and plant breeding and its applications to both food and non-food crops;
- Sustainable animal production systems, taking a systemic approach across all aspects of animal production;
- Quantification, monitoring and emission reduction of greenhouse gases in agriculture and forestry;
- A new funding instrument allowing less-developed bioeconomy regions to participate more effectively in the transition towards sustainability by supporting stronger mechanisms for knowledge transfer, capacity building and the deployment of existing solutions;
- Connecting research stakeholders along the whole value chain in the agri-food system, synergies, feedback loops and trade-offs;
- More specific attention to organic agriculture and food, and a stronger role for organic experts and stakeholders in research programming;
- A focus on innovation and value creation from biomass and biorefineries;

The report also calls for cross-cutting topics under the European Partnerships.

Part 2, “Paving the Road” gives an overview of practical knowledge, lessons learned, and hindsight ideas collected from the people working on the work packages and tasks in the GEH and the GEH networks.

The work includes feedback and ideas coming from:

- The CSA coordination
- The GEH call office
- The Socratic Dialogue Events
- Monitoring, Evaluation, and Impact Assessment
- Learnings on long-term impact
- The Living Archive
- Widening activities
- Support of Early Career Researchers
- Communication and Dissemination activities
- Learnings provided by project researchers

Together, part 1 and part 2 give an overview of the current position of the thematic areas of the GEH networks within the HEU funding landscape, and a practical set of lessons and ideas that may support future initiatives.

A photograph taken from inside a building, looking out through a stone archway. The archway is made of light-colored stone blocks. On either side of the arch are heavy wooden doors with metal hardware, including circular knockers and ornate hinges. The floor in the foreground is made of irregular stone tiles. Through the arch, a bright, sunny courtyard is visible. The courtyard has a dry, yellowish ground. In the background, there are several trees, including a large, thick-trunked tree and a brick pillar. The sky is blue with some light clouds.

GENERAL OUTLINE AND INTRODUCTION

1.1 General outline and introduction

The Green ERA-Hub (GEH) is a meta-network that brings together fifteen European research networks, including ERA-Nets, a European Joint Programme (EJP), and a self-sustained initiative in the fields of agriculture, food, and biotechnology. These networks have built more than two decades of experience in joint programming and have played an important role in coordinating national research programmes, strengthening international collaboration and supporting research that addresses major societal challenges.

The Green ERA-Hub has reached the end of its project after a runtime of four years. During this period, the European research and innovation landscape has changed considerably with the launch of the Horizon Europe European Partnerships and the ending of the ERA-Nets. This is a good moment to reflect on the continuity of the thematic research areas, and on the practical experience gained through many years of joint programming.

This report therefore consists of two complementary parts.

Part 1, "Staying on Track", looks back at the thematic areas covered by the fifteen Green ERA-Hub networks. These research areas were carefully developed over many years and remain highly relevant for addressing societal challenges and supporting the transition to a sustainable future. This report maps how well these thematic areas are currently covered in the European research and innovation landscape and it identifies research topics that may no longer be sufficiently addressed. Continuity in strategic research is important for preserving scientific expertise, and building on the impact achieved through previous joint programming activities.

Part 2, "Paving the Road", focuses on the transfer of practical knowledge gained through the years by people working together on joint programming activities. A lot of experience is built up during the lifetime of an ERA-Net. This knowledge resides with the people working on calls, supporting projects, and widening international collaboration. Formal deliverables report on the planned outcomes, but often the practical lessons and hindsight ideas for improvement are not documented. These insights are however very important to preserve for future initiatives. Also the project researchers who are funded through these networks gain relevant experience with the support mechanisms and can provide practical feedback on what worked, what didn't, and what was actually needed.

One of the objectives of the Green ERA-Hub is to preserve best practices and managerial competences developed through previous initiatives. This report contributes to that objective by bringing together a non-exhaustive collection of practical ideas, lessons learned and recommendations from the Green ERA-Hub work packages, tasks, and project researchers. The report is intended as a practical document sharing lessons learned that may support future European joint programming initiatives.

STAYING ON TRACK

2. STAYING ON TRACK

The main purpose of Green ERA-Hub's (GEH) roadmapping tasks are (i) to bring the scopes of the fifteen networks together, (ii) to map their research needs and (iii) to identify the priorities that were still standing and relevant within the changing European research area. Additionally the roadmapping activities searched for synergies between the networks, identified new research topics that emerged when the scopes of different networks were combined and aimed to bring the activities in line with the relevant EU policies and strategies in the thematic areas covered by the GEH.

With the roadmapping tasks we provide a solid basis underneath the scoping activities for the three calls that were launched by the GEH. Results are presented in Deliverable 2.1 *Green ERA-Hub Strategic Roadmapping Workshop*, the document [*The Green ERA-Hub networks Challenges, scopes and goals*](#), various internal documents used during the scoping process, and its inputs can be recognized in the topics covered within the calls launched by the GEH.

The GEH bridged the time between the ending ERA-Nets and the upcoming Partnerships. Relevant topics remained covered in this transition period. Now that the Partnerships are fully operational and the ERA-Nets have ended it is important to take a look back at the thematic areas covered by the ERA-Nets and identify which relevant topics are not included by the Partnerships and are at risk in being overlooked, resulting in increasing research gaps.

The final roadmapping activities included discussions with the coordinators of the individual networks and with the secretariat of FACCE JPI to assess how the thematic areas are currently covered within the European Research Area and to identify which topics require further attention.

2.1 Networks overview

The following overview presents the outcomes of the assessment of the thematic coverage of the GEH networks within the current European research and innovation landscape. Based on input from the coordinators of the individual networks and cross-checked against the findings of WP6 (Deliverable 6.1, *Final Guidelines for the Outreach*)¹, it identifies the extent to which the core topics of each network are covered within the current funding landscape and highlights research areas that remain insufficiently addressed.

The results show that there is considerable variation between the GEH networks ranging from core topics that are well covered in the current funding landscape, to core topics that are hardly addressed at all.

The most prominent topics that are insufficiently addressed according to the GEH networks are:

- Mitigation, adaptation and resilience to the effects of climate change on food systems from farm to fork;
- Addressing the integrated soil–freshwater–food systems–biomanufacturing nexus;

¹ Hippolyte I. Deliverable 6.1 Final guidelines for the outreach. The Green ERA-Hub, 2025.

- Research funding of lower TRLs in the area of biotechnology and its platform technologies;
- Effective trans-national (AU-EU), research, innovation and collaboration on joint challenges in agri, food and climate;
- Molecular plant science and plant breeding and its applications to both food and non-food crops;
- Sustainable animal production systems, taking a systemic approach across all aspects of animal production;
- Quantification, monitoring and emission reduction of greenhouse gasses in agriculture and forestry;
- A new funding instrument allowing less-developed bioeconomy regions to participate more effectively in the transition towards sustainability by supporting stronger mechanisms for knowledge transfer, capacity building and the deployment of existing solutions;
- Connecting research stakeholders along the whole value chain in the agri-food system, synergies, feedback loops and trade-offs;
- More specific attention to organic agriculture and food, and a stronger role for organic experts and stakeholders in research programming;
- A focus on innovation and value creation from biomass and biorefineries;

Table 2.1: Level of coverage of the thematic research area per network in the current European Horizon programme. GREEN – Topics are sufficiently covered; YELLOW – Topics are mostly covered, some details are missing; ORANGE – Relevant topics are missing, attention is needed; RED – Core topics are neglected, action is needed.

BIOEAST	ORANGE
CORE ORGANIC	ORANGE
EJP SOIL	GREEN
ERA CAPS	RED
ERA CO BIOTECH	RED
FACCE ERA-GAS	ORANGE
EUPHRESKO	GREEN
FOSC	RED
ICRAD	GREEN
ICT AGRI FOOD	ORANGE
LEAP AGRI	YELLOW
FACCE SURPLUS	ORANGE
SUSAN	RED
SUSCROP	ORANGE
SUSFOOD	GREEN
FACCE JPI	ORANGE

These topics show strong overlap with the outcomes of the GEH Work Package 6 work. WP6 focused on guidelines for widening activities and strengthened collaboration with EU-11 Member States, the Balkan

region, Mediterranean African countries, and a global approach. The results presented in Deliverable 6.1 include a list of key areas that are missing or underrepresented in the current Partnerships:

- Climate change as a core topic
- Continuum from primary production to food systems
- Biotechnology
- Basic research in plant science
- Organic farming
- Greenhouse gas emissions
- Transcontinental issues
- Sustainable animal farming (covered only in relation with health and welfare)
- Mixed farming (animal/crop)

WP6 also calls for joint cross-cutting calls under the European Partnerships, the development of pan-European research themes, and maturation calls that support the real-world implementation of successful research outcomes.

An additional prioritization exercise on the most relevant research topics was done with 43 researchers from 35 funded projects covering the full scope of the GEH. This workshop took place in Berlin on 11 October 2024.

The outcomes overlapped to a large extent with the topics identified by the GEH. Interestingly, the researchers did not prioritize many topics that are currently covered by the Partnerships, even though the Partnerships were not yet up to speed at that time. Instead, they prioritized many topics that, although specific, are highly interdisciplinary and systemic, and would fall under ‘**Inter-Partnership calls**’.

One of the highest prioritized ideas by researchers would be relevant for all thematic areas:

- Follow-up calls to increase TRL levels and support the implementation and scaling of successful projects

2.2 BIOEAST

ORANGE: ‘Relevant topics are missing, attention is needed’

The thematic priorities of BIOEAST are partially covered by existing European Partnerships and funding initiatives, notably Sustainable Food Systems, AGROECOLOGY, Water4All, Biodiversa+, Forests and Forestry, Agriculture of Data, Accelerating Farming Systems Transition, PRIMA, and the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU). These initiatives address important elements of sustainable agriculture, food systems, water management, biodiversity, forestry, and bioeconomy development.

However, several priorities of the BIOEAST macro-region remain insufficiently addressed. The main gap is not the absence of thematic coverage, but the lack of integrated approaches focused on the specific development needs of Central and Eastern Europe, including the Western Balkans, Ukraine, and Moldova.

Considering the eight European Partnerships BIOEAST identifies four thematic areas requiring additional attention:

Soil priorities insufficiently addressed:

- Closing yield gaps and improving ecosystem services in erosion- and desertification-prone areas.
- Scientific understanding and management of fertile black soils and reutilisation of marginal and urban soils.
- Strengthening advisory systems and institutional support for sustainable soil management.
- Accelerating deployment and uptake of research results in practice.
- Improving cooperation between public and private actors, including land users and investors.

Freshwater priorities insufficiently addressed:

- Integrated land and watershed management, including restoration of small water cycles.
- Nature-based solutions, rainwater harvesting, and aquifer recharge.
- Sustainable agricultural practices supporting freshwater management.
- Blue-green infrastructure and digital water technologies.
- Freshwater-based bioeconomy development, including aquatic biomass valorisation and aquaculture.

Food Systems priorities insufficiently addressed:

- Agroecology-based sustainable food systems.
- Food justice and equitable value distribution along food chains.
- True-cost accounting of food production.
- Understanding trade-offs and policy conflicts within food systems.
- Diversification of sustainable protein sources.

Local Biomass Valorisation priorities insufficiently addressed:

- Skills development and specialised bioeconomy education.
- Strengthening R&I capacities in less-developed regions.
- Awareness and acceptance of bio-based solutions.
- Biodiversity-compatible biomass supply systems.
- Local biomass infrastructure and small- and medium-scale biorefineries.

Overall, BIOEAST considers that current partnerships provide important foundations but do not yet fully address the integrated soil–freshwater–food systems–biomanufacturing nexus required to unlock the sustainable bioeconomy potential of the Central and Eastern European macro-region.

Considering the two treaty-based Art. 185 and Art. 187 partnerships, beyond thematic coverage, BIOEAST identifies important structural gaps in the current European partnership landscape.

The experience of BIOEAST demonstrates that the challenge is not only which topics are funded, but also how research and innovation funding is organised and deployed across European regions.

- The PRIMA Partnership provides a valuable example of a geographically focused research and innovation initiative. Through targeted calls, smaller and more focused consortia, long-term regional cooperation, science diplomacy, and the active involvement of neighbouring countries, PRIMA has successfully strengthened knowledge exchange and innovation capacities across the

Mediterranean region. Similar mechanisms could provide significant benefits for the Central and Eastern European macro-region, including EU Member States, the Western Balkans, Ukraine, and Moldova.

- The Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU) plays a critical role in supporting excellence-driven bioeconomy innovation, and industrial deployment. However, its current intervention logic is primarily focused on developing new technologies and flagship investments. Less attention is given to the transfer, adaptation, and replication of already demonstrated bio-based solutions in regions with lower innovation and industrial capacities. For many Central and Eastern European countries, the main challenge is not the generation of additional technological excellence, but the effective uptake, adaptation and deployment of existing solutions, business models, and biorefinery concepts.
- BIOEAST therefore sees a need for future European funding instruments that complement excellence-based innovation support with stronger mechanisms for knowledge transfer, capacity building, technology adaptation, demonstration, and regional deployment, enabling less-developed bioeconomy regions to participate more effectively in the European transition towards a sustainable and circular bioeconomy.

2.3 CORE ORGANIC

ORANGE: 'Relevant topics are missing, attention is needed'

The CORE Organic work focusing on organic farming is partly covered by the Partnership AGROECOLOGY and the ERA-Nets work focusing on organic food is partly covered by the Partnership FutureFoodS. The analysis of the selected projects by these Partnerships shows nonetheless that relevant topics are missing or it is not possible to assess their relevance for the organics. Projects focussing on organic research are possible under the calls from these Partnerships, but that doesn't guarantee that organic topics are covered. CORE Organic indicates that addressing organic topics in the Partnerships is a relevant layer for supporting R&I and the EU policy food and farming visions, but it needs to be strengthened through adequate inclusion in the transnational calls together with developing of sectoral (thematic) evaluation and monitoring mechanisms in order to really benefit the aera. There is a need for more structural inclusion of organic research across the Partnerships:

- Include specific references to organic agriculture and food in the vision, mission, and SRIA
- Integrate provisions on organic in the calls texts and involve organic food/farming experts in the project evaluations
- Integrate organic impact indicators in project monitoring mechanisms that can indicate which research results are 'specific to' or 'relevant for' organic sector R&I
- Integrate systematic collection of data from the projects indicating share of budgets allocated for organics (e.g., specific organic farmers or companies, etc.)
- Integrate organic experts and stakeholders in the Scientific and Stakeholder Advisory Board
- Involve organic stakeholders in the design of the SRIA
- Coordinate support for organic R&I between Partnerships

2.4 EJP SOIL

GREEN: 'Topics are sufficiently covered'

The topic of soil is currently well covered in the European funding landscape. There is a sufficient focus on soil in the Horizon programme through Cluster 6, EU Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe', and several topics within the AGROECOLOGY Partnership SRIA are relevant to soil research.

A point of attention is the need for sustained funding over time, ensuring that relevant work continues and that insights are brought into practice.

A current initiative from Climate-KIC that addresses this point is the Soil Innovation Partnership. This initiative aims to bring relevant outcomes from EJP SOIL closer to the market. However, the initiative is still under development, and it is uncertain whether it will be realised.

2.5 ERA CAPS

RED: 'Core topics are neglected, action is needed'

The scope of ERA-CAPS covers all areas of **molecular plant science** to answer **fundamental biological questions** of relevance working towards:

- Food and Nutrition Security: research that contributes to the sustainable and secure supply of safe and nutritious food for an increasing global population. This includes yield optimisation, quality traits and nutrient use efficiency, amongst other research areas.
- Non-food crops: this theme includes research into crops (or appropriate models) where the end-use includes bioenergy or industrial biotechnology.
- Adaptation to a changing climate: research that addresses how plants can adapt, or be adapted, to grow in a changing environment.
- Biotic/abiotic stresses: this theme includes research into plant responses to either biotic or abiotic stress, or how plants contend with a combination of biotic and abiotic stresses.

These topics are not addressed at a molecular plant science level as a dedicated priority in the current landscape of European Partnerships.

The AGROECOLOGY partnership covers some of the same strategic end-goals as ERA-CAPS where plant-related research contributes to agroecological transitions, resilience, sustainability, and reduced-input agriculture. However, AGROECOLOGY does not prioritise molecular mechanisms, genomics, gene regulation, signalling pathways, or other core molecular plant science topics.

The scientific understanding of fundamental plant biology and its applications to both food and non-food crops remains highly relevant in today's advanced, innovation-driven agriculture. Molecular plant science has contributed to significant improvements in agricultural capabilities, including higher yields with lower inputs in a changing climate. Continued innovation in these areas is an essential and complementary component of the systemic agricultural transition that is addressed by AGROECOLOGY.

2.6 ERA COBIOTECH

RED: ‘Core topics are neglected, action is needed’

ERA CoBioTech – an ERA-Net Cofund of the second implementation wave with a duration from 12/2016 until 11/2021 – arose from three predecessor lines:

- the ERA-Nets on systems biology: ERASysBio, ERASysBioPlus, and ERASysApp;
- the two ERA-Nets on industrial biology: ERA-IB 1 & 2; and
- the stand-alone ERA-Net on synthetic biology: ERASynBio.

With ERA CoBioTech these three funding lines were amalgamated in order to form one strong coordination action in **biotechnology** and, more importantly, on platform technologies in the remit of biotechnology.

Consequently, all three calls implemented by ERA CoBioTech were centered around biotechnology as a key enabling technology for a bio-based economy in order to tackle societal challenges such as decarbonisation of the economy and reduction of the dependence on fossil feedstocks. ERA CoBioTech’s three transnational research calls aimed at projects from TRL 2 to TRL 6 addressing:

- Sustainable production and conversion of different types of feedstocks and bioresources into value-added products;
- New products, value-added products, and supply services; and
- Sustainable industrial processes.

ERA CoBioTech’s technology-driven approach significantly differed from all other ERA-Net Cofunds convening in the Green ERA-Hub GEH, which were driven by the “societal challenges” as outlined under the framework programme Horizon 2020. Further, ERA CoBioTech was endowed with the double amount of EU-contribution (10 Mio €) compared to the other initiatives, resulting in the **largest co-funded call in agriculture and biotech** conducted under Horizon 2020: National contribution, EU-TopUp, and project partners’ own contributions summed up to **~40 mio €**.

Already during ERA CoBioTech’s runtime the EU installed an institutionalised PPP under §187 AEUV, termed BBI-JU. BBI-JU was an industry-driven programme aiming at accelerating the innovation process and market development. At this time this was a perfect match as ERA CoBioTech addressed applied basic research (TRL 2-TRL 6, exclusively) whereas BBI was focused on industry-driven applications and technology development of higher TRL numbers.

However, under Horizon Europe a remarkable misbalance arose. Whereas BBI-JU was continued as CBE-JU with comparable goals, no analogue successor for ERA CoBioTech was put in place. Thus, ERA CoBioTech’s remit **is not at all addressed in the programme context of Horizon Europe.**

This results for instance in a drastic oversubscription of CBE JU’s calls for lower TRL research. Similarly, Green ERA-Hub’s third call experienced the same phenomenon when asking for proposals on “Biotechnological applications to improve the utilisation of biomass”. This underlines the **urgent need for lower TRL research funding** in the area of **biotechnology** and its platform technologies in the context European research funding.

2.7 FACCE ERA-GAS

ORANGE: ‘Relevant topics are missing, attention is needed’

There are three core-topics from FACCE ERA-GAS that are currently not covered by current initiatives :

- GHG emissions quantification, accounting, and inventories in agriculture and forestry (e.g. moving to higher tier inventory methodologies, harmonising inventories across Europe)
- GHG emissions monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) from agriculture and forestry
- Assessment of policy and economic measures to support emissions reductions across the farm-to-fork and forest-to-consumer chain

The Partnerships AGROECOLOGY, FOREST, and Agriculture of Data are sufficiently covering the following two FACCE ERA-GAS core-topics:

- Refining and facilitating the implementation of GHG mitigation technologies in agriculture and forestry
- State-of-the-art production systems that are profitable and improve food and forest biomass production while reducing GHG emissions

2.8 EUPHRESKO

GREEN: ‘Topics are sufficiently covered by the continuing work of Euphresco’

Euphresco is a self-sustained network that keeps being supported by its partners and continues to launch new calls for proposals to cover the core topics as defined by the SRIA.

2.9 FOSC

RED: ‘Core topics are neglected, action is needed’

The Partnerships AGROECOLOGY and FutureFoodS and the International Research Consortium cover a limited part of FOSCs core topics. The topic of sustainable and healthy food systems is covered in the Partnerships, but the link between Europe and the African continent is not included. Additionally, the major impact of climate change on the resilience of food systems is mostly neglected. The impact of climate change on food systems and mitigation and adaptation to climate change has a limited role in the Partnerships and is often addressed indirectly. Projects funded by these Partnerships may have a positive impact on food systems under climate change, but this is not guaranteed. To secure sustainable and reliable food systems a stronger focus is needed on:

- Effective trans-national (AU-EU), research, innovation and collaboration on food and nutrition security and sustainable agriculture under climate change;
- Assessment of climate change-related risks for food value chains, including impacts on producers, prices, availability, quality, international trade and food security, and resulting changes in consumer behaviours;
- Development of innovative solutions to cope with the multiple risks and challenges to the food systems posed by global environmental changes and system shocks.

2.10 ICRAD

GREEN: 'Topics are sufficiently covered'

The thematic area of ICRAD is sufficiently covered by the European Partnership on Animal Health and Welfare.

2.11 ICT AGRI FOOD

ORANGE: 'Relevant topics are missing, attention is needed'

The two EU Partnerships Agriculture of Data and FutureFoodS are covering many objectives of ICT AGRI FOOD. However, the major objective of ICT AGRI FOOD is not covered any longer:

- To connect stakeholders along the whole value chain of agri-food systems to develop synergies from farm to fork.

While the Partnerships Agriculture of Data and AGROECOLOGY are covering agriculture and FutureFoodS is covering the post-farmgate part of the agri-food system, there is no wholistic approach anymore and the understanding of feedback loops along the whole value chain is not included.

Moreover, as Agriculture of Data is strongly focusing on satellite data and earth observation, animal husbandry runs a risk to be a bit underrepresented, as one cannot look into the stables. Technologies for the animal sector are welcome and also part of Agriculture of Data, but the number of Use Cases addressing data and technology for the animal sector is likely disproportionately small if compared to the number of Use Cases on the crop production sector.

2.12 LEAP AGRI

YELLOW: 'Topics are mostly covered, some details are missing'

The interests of LEAP AGRI are mostly covered by the International Research Consortium (IRC) and the Consortium Europe Africa on Research and Innovation for Food Systems Transformation (CEA-FIRST). However, additional focus on research projects on locally adapted innovations, ensuring that regional specificities and community needs on FNSSA is required.

2.13 FACCE SURPLUS

ORANGE: 'Relevant topics are missing, attention is needed'

Sustainable, efficient, and resilient agricultural production systems for food and non-food systems is the core of FACCE SURPLUS. These topics are partly covered by the Partnership AGROECOLOGY. However, biorefinery is a core topic of FACCE SURPLUS and is currently not sufficiently covered by other initiatives.

- Innovation and value creation from biomass and biorefineries in synergy with the environmentally sustainable intensification of agricultural and other biomass production

- Innovations in the design and siting of environmentally advanced, minimum waste biorefineries
- Small-scale biorefinery concepts and their potential role in enhancing the sustainability and productivity of EU agriculture

2.14 SUSAN

RED: 'Core topics are neglected, action is needed'

The core topic of SusAn (Sustainable Animal Production Systems) and the SCAR Collaborative Working Group - Sustainable Animal Production (CWG SAP) are currently being neglected and action is needed.

There are currently two funding initiatives that funded projects on animal production, the GEH and EUPAHW. The GEH funded one project, on the measurement of enteric methane, which is not typical for the SusAn approach. EUPAHW features four topics under Action 4 and Action 6 of its SRIA that have links to the scope of SusAn, however, the topics remain well within the scope of EUPAHW and the SCAR Collaborative Working Group - Animal Health and Welfare (CWG AHW), which is different from the scope of SusAn and the CWG SAP.

A stronger focus on research on sustainable animal production systems, taking a systemic approach across all aspects of animal production, is needed to address the major challenges facing European livestock systems.

The ERA-NET SusAn was based on the following concepts:

1. System thinking which perceives animal production as a complex set of interdependent system components like animal health, welfare, breeding, feeding, housing, manure management, etc. The animal production system may be investigated as a whole or key components of the system may be identified that can cause relevant changes of the system's performance.
2. Sustainable development which means meeting the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The three pillars of sustainability, economy, environment, and society, need to be considered of equal importance.

SusAn identified the following major challenges for European livestock production systems:

- To achieve food and nutrition security
- To restrict emissions and nutrient losses
- To keep resource use within planetary boundaries
- To preserve and enhance biodiversity
- To support rural livelihoods
- To provide high standards of animal health and welfare

Key messages regarding challenges

- All challenges must be met simultaneously and in accordance with set targets. Therefore, the above-named challenges are not ranked.

- The challenges are interdependent and need to be tackled within a systems-based approach in order to account for potential synergies and trade-offs.

The SusAn SRIA lists single components of livestock production systems

The design of livestock production systems involves combinations of its basic components like animal health, animal nutrition, genetics, housing and manure management, in order to tackle the challenges for European livestock production:

SusAn divided the components of livestock production systems into two parts:

- » political and socio-economic system components, and
- » agricultural and technical system components.

Political and socio-economic system components:

- Governance and public policy
- Market and prices
- Consumption patterns and food waste
- Working conditions

Agricultural and technical system components:

- Animal nutrition
- Breeding / genetics
- Animal housing
- Manure management incl. biogas
- Animal health and welfare management
- ICT, robotics and Big Data

Key messages regarding single system components

- To achieve major changes, a systems approach is required and more than one system component needs to be changed.
- Political/socio-economic components are at least as important for a transformation of the livestock sector as agricultural/technical components.

2.15 SUSCROP

ORANGE: 'Relevant topics are missing, attention is needed'

SusCrop aimed to strengthen the European Research Area in the field of Sustainable Crop Production. It defined four major strategic objectives to contribute to this field, of which one key-topic is not covered anymore in the current funding landscape:

- Enhancement of predictive breeding technologies and development of new genotypes leading to new phenotypes and crop varieties

SusCrop flagged that agro-biodiversity as a key-topic needs plant breeding as research topic for the production of new and improved crop varieties to cope with the consequences of climate change. This is currently not part of the scope of the Partnerships.

Other key-topics of SusCrop are sufficiently covered by AGROECOLOGY:

- Integrated pest management and integrated crop management
- Resource efficiency in cropping systems
- Agricultural crops as part of an ecosystem.

2.16 SUSFOOD

GREEN: 'Topics are sufficiently covered'

The thematic area of SUSFOOD is sufficiently covered by the Partnership FutureFoodS.

2.17 FACCE JPI

ORANGE: 'Relevant topics are missing, attention is needed'

The FACCE-JPI SRIA core themes are only partially covered by existing European Partnerships and Missions. While some elements are addressed, significant gaps remain across several priority areas.

Certain topics from the FACCE-JPI SRIA are included in Partnerships such as AGROECOLOGY, for example Core Theme 4, "Trade-offs and synergies between food production, ecosystems and climate". However, the climate dimension within this theme is insufficiently addressed.

Core Theme 2, "Sustainable and resilient agriculture", is comparatively well covered by the AGROECOLOGY Partnership.

Core Theme 1, "An agricultural sector that contributes to climate neutrality", is completely missing. This is especially the case for intensive farming systems and any non-agroecological farming. This is especially the case within the livestock sector. There appears to be no opportunities for research specifically targeting climate mitigation in intensive livestock systems.

PRIMA partially covers FACCE topics, but its activities are strongly regionally focused and place greater emphasis on adaptation than on mitigation. Similarly, the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change does not focus on agriculture and food.

The initiative most closely aligned with FACCE priorities is the Soil Mission, but it focuses strictly on soils and does not include food, nutrition, and food security dimensions, which are part of Core Theme 3, "Nutrition-sensitive agricultural production for food security".

The main gaps identified are the following:

Mitigation and adaptation of livestock systems and agriculture

- Strategies to reduce GHG emissions based on improved understanding of the microbiome of soils and animals
- Specific technologies for reducing methane and nitrous oxide from livestock, manure systems and soils
- Genetic improvement of plants and animals with lower emissions. Particularly for grassland-based systems, there's a gap in research
- Research on tropical livestock systems is important to understand the effects of European imports
- Circular livestock systems and their role in climate mitigation and their relation to diets.

Climate impacts on nutrition, health and food systems

- Climate impact on the nutritional value of food
- Climate impact on the connections between health, climate, food and production.

This last topic was partially started through collaboration with Healthy Diet Healthy Lives but as FACCE is ending there is no home for this type of research.

2.18 RESEARCHER INPUT

On 10-11 October 2024 the Joint Conference was organised by the Green ERA-Hub and FACCE-JPI. The conference was attended by a total of 43 researchers from 35 projects funded by the Green ERA-Hub, FACCE SUSCROP, ERA CoBioTech, FOSC, the SUSFOOD2 and Core Organic joint call, and SUSCROP.

The researchers participated in the workshop *“Designing the Future”*. The aim was to engage the research community in identifying key research gaps, emerging insights, and future research needs within their respective fields, with a focus on identifying the most relevant research topics.

The outcomes of the workshop are presented below. Topics that are fully covered by the Partnerships AGROECOLOGY, FutureFoods, EUPAHW and AgData are written in *Italic script*.

All thematic areas:

- Follow up calls to increase TRL levels and support the implementation and scaling of successful projects

Climate

- Breeding technologies for resilient and climate-proof plant and animal production systems
- Carbon farming as key-contributor to climate change mitigation
- Impact of the Nitrogen cycle on climate
- Microbiome-based point-source CO₂ sequestration in food systems
- Carbon sequestration by upcycling agricultural side-streams into long lasting materials
- *Impact of subsidies on both unsustainable and sustainable production systems*

Sustainable livestock production systems

- Circular livestock production systems

- Sustainable livestock density per hectare of land globally
- GHG reduction in livestock production systems
- Local, equitable, and balanced (animal)protein production systems
- Microbiome-based strategies to mitigate emissions from livestock production systems
- Use of animal waste products in circular systems
- Consumer engagement and awareness on livestock production
- Genetic diversity in animal production

Crop sciences

- Using CRISPR genome editing for resilient crops
- The opportunities in GMO development
- Locally adapted species
- Breeding for disease and pest resistance in crops, and drought and salt tolerant species
- Plants as meta-organisms: endosphere, rhizosphere, phyllosphere, and including plant-plant interaction

Sustainable agriculture

- Soil Health versus One Health, and the impact of soil contaminants
- Food production modelling, including on farm data, environmental conditions, management practices, resource availability, human activities, and long-term resilience
- *Farmer as food producer, landscape manager and steward of biodiversity*
- *Molecular tools as biological control agents*
- *Community and education oriented agricultural projects*
- *Diversity and intercropping for resilient production systems*

Sustainable food systems

- Quantification of true costs made in the entire food value chain
- One Health in the entire food value chain, from production to consumer health, including the microbiome
- Circular food systems
- Efficiency in high intensity food production systems
- *Whole foods versus highly processed food impact on health and environment*
- *Role of governance of fair, reliable, and sustainable food systems*
- *Food justice and food system diversity*
- *Local food production systems and producer-consumer interactions*
- *Impact and opportunities of long term land use, including land use governance*
- *Data integration systems connecting food system actors*
- *Digital tools, smart farming and use of satellites in food production systems*
- *Robotics in plant production systems*
- *Role of industry and commerce in fair, healthy, and reliable food systems*

A close-up photograph of two green wheat stalks in the foreground, with a bright sun visible in the background, creating a soft, golden glow. The wheat stalks are in sharp focus, showing the texture of the grain and the long awns. The background is a blurred green field under a bright sky.

PAVING THE ROAD

3. PAVING THE ROAD

This chapter presents a collection of learnings and practical insights derived from the work done in the Green ERA-Hub and the GEH networks. Knowledge within Joint Programming networks is not limited to reports and formal outputs, it also lives in the people who drive these initiatives. Their experiences often show that practice is different from theory, and that, in hindsight, it might be smarter to do things in a different way. Many of these insights are at risk of being lost because they are not included in official deliverables and reports. In addition, researchers involved in GEH and ERA-Net funded projects bring their own needs, and suggestions, which can strengthen future networks.

This chapter is designed as a practical document that captures a non-exhaustive set of ideas, insights, and lessons learned from the GEH work packages and the researchers involved in its projects. The goal is to provide practical takeaways that can support work in future initiatives.

3.1 Learnings from CSA coordination

Background

The Green ERA-Hub fully achieved its goal to maintain the momentum and experience gained over the last 18 years of trans-national research programming in ERA-Net (Co-fund)s and to use the vast experience of its partners to:

- Continue to build on previous achievements and further enhance cross-sector collaborations through implementation of new joint calls;
- Continue valorisation and implementation of other joint activities supporting the market, regulatory or societal uptake of results after the end of individual ERA-Nets;
- Identify common research and innovation priorities,
- Preserve best practice and managerial competences;
- Contribute to the planning and complement the implementation of the new EU Partnerships and Missions;
- Broaden the actions and impact of initiatives towards stakeholders and in terms of geographical coverage;
- Contribute to achieve the strategic goals of the SDGs, in particular zero hunger, industry innovation and infrastructure, responsible consumption and production, life on land, partnership for the goals, the farm2fork strategy and EU's Green Deal.

Main learnings and suggestions

The EU's legal provisions for CSAs remain virtually unchanged, making the framework clear and unambiguous for both parties – the EU and the consortium, making the handling very efficient. With 11 beneficiaries and one associated partner, spread across 8 work packages, the project was manageable and, in terms of coordination effort, comparable to the earlier ERA-Nets or ERA-Net cofunds. In contrast, the newly introduced EU partnerships are vastly larger and significantly more complex to coordinate (Fig. 3.1). While the coordination of the Green ERA-Hub could be handled by a single person, the EU partnerships generally require teams of up to ~5 FTE to ensure the proper fulfilment of all contractual obligations.

CSA (GREEN ERA-Hub)	previous ERA-Net (Cofund)s	EU Partnerships
10-20 partners	20-30 partners	50-100 partners
3-4 years	5 years	7-10 years
2-4 Mio. € EC	5 Mio. € EC	100-150 Mio. € EC
<1 Mio. € EC/year	~1 Mio. € EC/year	~15 Mio. € EC/year

Figure 3.1: Comparison of the key characteristics of the EU instruments CSA, ERA-Net (Cofund), and Partnerships

While implementing our activities, we found that we were able to address many challenges (e.g., defining call topics, coordinating documents, adapting content, etc.) very quickly - much faster than would have been the case with the large EU partnerships. The Green ERA-Hub has proven - to stay with the metaphor in Fig 3.1- to be a very fast sailboat navigating among the very large tankers.

3.2 Learnings from organizing the GEH calls

Background

In a context marked by global challenges and complex interdependencies, deepening the collaboration with/in the ERA towards new or less engaged countries, including non-European, is a key objective of future policy coordination and research funding initiatives.

Feedback from some non-EU funding bodies was on the whole supportive of the GEH funding model and willing to establish a collaboration.

However, to develop these collaborations, it is necessary to overcome some obstacles and to activate appropriate levers. Some challenges and related solutions are more specific to certain countries and macro-regions; others are more general.

Achievements

1. Potential partners identified that could become partners in a future program.
2. Some newly contacted funders were able to join the GEH Calls, which was a tremendous success given the short timeframe.
3. WI (Wheat Initiative) member countries are now aware of the Green ERA Hub and related funding coordination opportunities
4. Learning: **Spending mutual time and effort for widening is fruitful in terms of networking, awareness and even in the (relatively) short term can get to working collaboration.**

Main learnings and suggestions

1. For some funders, budget request to be placed in autumn of the preceding year. **The timing for the budget must be carefully considered to enable funders' participation.**
2. The best type of contact depends on national-regional specificities. For example: researchers can be a better entry point to mobilise their funders, rather than contacting funders directly. **Identification of the "right" contacts is crucial for a timely and effective start of the collaboration.**
3. Human resources: the generational aspect has a specific relevance. There can be lower interest by well established ("older") researchers/administrative staff, sometimes even due to limited knowledge of the English language. A "generational renewal" will bring in younger generations, likely with appropriate skills and interest. **Younger generations of funders and researchers are a lever for promoting stronger international cooperation.**
4. Changes in staff can also be critical, witnessing a high process dependence on personal commitment. **Understanding of funding rules and awareness of advantages for collaboration should permeate through the management and decision-making structures of the funding agencies.**
5. Committed colleagues in funders' organisations but low in hierarchies, can be useful entry points for communication, as well as individual researchers or RPOs, but they need support to trigger interest from penholders. **Endorsement letters by ERA funders and/or EC can trigger interest by the hierarchies and give stronger legitimation to the proposals for collaborations.**
6. New funders can be concerned to lose control over their budget, as they are new to the process. Common pot procedures were explained, but call timelines may have been too fast to leave enough time for decision making for those funders not already familiar with the funding scheme. Concerns could be how national/regional funds might be spent and how relevant future funded projects might be to national research priorities. Besides, concern can arise for signing documents perceived (sometimes mis-perceived) as legally binding. Maybe starting cooperation in a multilateral European scheme was too ambitious in some cases. Possible solution: **Less complex bilateral/trilateral cooperations can be taken into consideration and explored, as a form of collaboration itself, but also as a way for gaining awareness and experience, and to pave the way to multilateral collaboration in a second stage.**
7. An additional possible obstacle is the perception of too broad research topics for new funders with the need to have clear research focus. It can be useful, in these cases, to **prepare calls with a range of different topics, even very specific ones, allowing funders to fund only those that fit in their research programmes.** However, a fragmented call with topics funded by one or very few funders should be avoided.
8. With particular focus on non-European contexts, it can be particularly difficult to establish collaboration with some countries. The involvement of funders capable to fund research groups in different countries can help. Example ACIAR: funds were provided to aid partners (a joint project with Ethiopia, Australia, and Germany was supported). Organisations able to support research activities beyond their national boundaries include GRDC, and ACIAR from Australia, FFAR USA, and aid agencies in Canada. **Cross boarder funding can strongly support the widening**

of a calls' geographical scope, also as an entry point for subsequent contacts with national funders.

9. **When a funder or a country, once contacted, indicate their low interest or their difficulties on joining, it is important to understand the reasons for these reactions, and to explore if – in the same country, there are different funders with a more compatible funding scheme and mechanisms.**

Additional learnings on specific research topics

1. **Energy-related topics generally raised low interest among research groups.** Maybe because they include priorities and need competences that are more easily retrievable in other research remits (also beyond cluster 6).
2. **Biotech and high-tech research topics, also more oriented towards basic research, could be better explored in future calls.**
3. **Research topics may sometimes reflect different cultural or disciplinary perspectives which can be perceived as opposing rather than complementary.** While this can lead to funding and exploring alternative solutions, it also risks overlooking potential synergies, especially when the different approaches (e.g., biotech vs. traditional methods) are perceived as incompatible rather than as opportunities for collaboration.

3.3 Learnings from the Socratic Dialogue Events

Background

The Green ERA-Hub (GEH) places strong emphasis on knowledge transfer as a core element of European Joint Programming cooperation. Through its WP5 initiative, GEH brings together the experiences of its members to collect, share, and adapt best practices from over 20 years of transnational R&I collaboration, including past ERA-Nets and related initiatives. The goal is to strengthen future cooperation among research program owners and managers, whether within Horizon Europe Partnerships or other transnational R&I funding frameworks.

As part of this effort, WP5 '*Knowledge transfer of best practices for transnational cooperation*' organised four Annual Socratic Dialogue Events (2023–2026), creating a platform for partners to exchange insights. These events preserved and expanded best practices, fostering mutual learning between GEH members and experts from Central and Eastern Europe, the Balkans, and the Mediterranean. Together, they addressed key challenges in agri-food research and innovation across the European Research Area (ERA).

Main learnings and suggestions

Open knowledge exchange between researchers, policy officers, funders and experts creates added value. There is an opportunity to strengthen dialogue and move beyond widening practices by establishing new structures for two-way mutual learning and exchange.

The main takeaway from organizing Socratic Dialogue Events is that long-term participation in transnational initiatives has helped European partners to build a shared understanding of transnational

cooperation, establishing common principles, practices, and goals on R&I activities. Through the Socratic Dialogue Events, this knowledge is not only preserved but also expanded via mutual learning between Green ERA-Hub consortium members and experts from the partner countries. This approach moves beyond widening practices and contributes to the establishment of new structures for knowledge exchange. The two-way exchange strengthens cooperation and highlights the importance of continuing such dialogue platforms to ensure sustainable, transformative, and inclusive future agri-food collaboration.

Learning aspects:

1. The benefits of participation in transnational funding activities should be clearly communicated to funders. Thematic webinars and knowledge-exchange activities are effective ways to transfer this information.
2. It is important to understand the priorities of ministries and funding organisations before engaging them in discussions on future collaboration.
3. Careful planning of international meetings and events (back-to-back) can create opportunities to engage with funders and peers more efficiently.
4. Synergies between GEH work packages supported the participation of new funding agencies in the transnational calls (e.g. Bosnia and Herzegovina).

3.4 Learnings from Monitoring Evaluation and Impact Assessment

Background

Making MEIA useful

Experience from more than 10 years of work on Monitoring, Evaluation and Impact Assessment (MEIA) across more than 15 ERA-Nets and joint programming initiatives shows that MEIA can be much more than a reporting obligation:

When designed well, MEIA can help programmes understand their achievements and successes, identify where difficulties occurred, and determine how future initiatives can be improved. However, this only works if MEIA is planned early, implemented realistically, and linked to decision-making.

Main learnings and suggestions

Design MEIA from the beginning

MEIA is often introduced too late in the programme cycle. This limits its value. A **clear MEIA concept** from the outset should define the key questions, the expected pathways from activities to outputs, outcomes, and potential impacts, and the practical mechanisms for collecting and using evidence. Objectives, indicators, data sources, reporting formats and responsibilities should be agreed before projects start.

Future initiatives should define early:

- What do we want to learn, and when?
- Which evidence do we need?

- Who will collect and use the data?
- Which future decisions should MEIA inform?

Moreover, MEIA expertise should be continuously involved so that monitoring concepts, programme objectives and strategic learning evolve together.

Be realistic about impact: impact takes time.

This is especially relevant for three-year research projects, often working at early TRLs. At project end, it is usually possible to observe:

- outputs, such as publications, tools, reports or datasets;
- early outcomes, such as new collaborations, capacities or follow-up activities;
- first impact signals, such as stakeholder interest or potential policy relevance.

However, **long-term societal, environmental, economic or policy impact usually cannot be fully measured immediately after project completion.**

Future initiatives should therefore distinguish clearly between outputs, **outcomes, impact signals and real long-term impact.** MEIA should describe plausible pathways to impact, without creating expectations that cannot realistically be met within the project lifetime.

Treat indicators as learning tools, not just numbers.

Indicators are often expected to provide simple numbers. Numbers are useful, but only if they answer a meaningful question.

A good indicator needs clarity on:

- What question does it answer?
- What value is being measured?
- How will the data be collected?
- When is a result considered successful, or when is further effort needed?

The same topic can be measured in several ways. For example, stakeholder engagement can mean the number of events, the diversity of stakeholders, the quality of interaction, or the uptake of results. Each tells a different story. Therefore, indicators should be **specific** enough to support analysis, but **flexible** enough to reflect the **diversity** of projects, disciplines, countries and stakeholder contexts.

Build harmonised, usable and well-governed data systems.

Data collection is often time-consuming. If templates are unclear, or if data are collected in different formats, the information may be difficult to analyse later.

Future initiatives should invest in **clear and harmonised data collection systems** from the start. This includes:

- common definitions;
- unambiguous templates;
- structured reporting formats;
- clear data responsibilities;
- realistic data protection procedures.

Harmonised data is especially valuable when results are compared across projects, calls or networks. Larger and more consistent datasets make MEIA findings more informative.

However, harmonisation should not become a rigid “one system fits all” approach. Networks, calls, and projects differ. A good MEIA system needs common core elements, but also enough **flexibility for specific contexts**.

Data management should therefore be reliable, transparent and balanced. Confidential data, personal data, expert opinions and stakeholder feedback require careful handling, including GDPR compliance, anonymisation where necessary, and clear access rights.

Close the learning loop.

The weakest part of MEIA is often the final step: **using the results**. Reports are written, but by the time findings are available, the next call or programme may already be under preparation. As a result, useful lessons may arrive too late to influence future planning.

A strong MEIA system fosters a learning culture. Funding agencies, ministries, programme managers, researchers and other stakeholders need time and **openness to discuss** what worked, what did not work as expected, and what could be improved.

Future initiatives should establish deliberate mechanisms to ensure that MEIA findings are discussed and used. This could include:

- reflection meetings before new calls are designed;
- short learning briefs for funders and programme managers;
- explicit decision points where MEIA findings are considered;
- a smart system that makes monitoring findings available early and in a usable format.

MEIA should not end with a report. Its real potential lies in whether the evidence helps to improve future action.

Overall advice

From the outset, MEIA should be designed as a way to support learning. It should be balanced, realistic and useful, combining harmonised data with contextual interpretation and linking evidence to the decisions that shape future programmes. The most important question is not only **whether a programme performed well**, but also what **can be learnt** from its implementation, results and limitations.

3.5 Learnings on Impact

Is anyone *really* monitoring impact?

The following learnings and suggestions are published both in this deliverable and as a stand-alone [publication](#)². It is part of the work done in Work Package 5 study on research impact.

² Rojas-Padilla, E. (2026). Is anyone really monitoring impact? - Research Highlights Report. Green ERA-Hub. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21036659>

Background

Why this research highlights matters

A qualitative and quantitative mixed-methods coding analysis of official reports from 15 research networks in the Green ERA-Hub (GEH) and supported by interviews to project and network managers, suggest that current monitoring tools for international research cooperation in the HE programme are better suited to demonstrating accountability and transparency than to tracking actual impact. In practice, impact assessment often relies on strong assumptions about knowledge transfer rather than evidence of – or contribution to – change or who benefited from research outputs. This gap becomes more evident since the European Commission’s shift from a logic-model approach to a Theory of Change, operationalised through the Pathways to Impact framework³. The change of logic-model calls for a corresponding shift in evaluation practice. Moreover, the Pathways to Impact framework require tailored indicators, longer time horizons, and follow-up mechanisms that extend beyond the formal end of research programmes.

While developing adjusted key performance indicators (KPIs) for Scientific and Economic Impact is relatively straightforward, Policy and Societal Impact remain poorly defined, weakly traced, and inadequately assessed. Yet these pathways are central to demonstrating progress towards European policy goals and the uptake of scientific and technological developments by society, highlighting the importance of science-policy interfaces.

Main learnings and suggestions

Core findings

1. Current reporting often makes assumptions of impact based on metrics of accountability, like website visits or number of participants in a workshop, rather than evidencing a particular effect or establishing targeted knowledge transfer activities.
2. Multiple definitions of impact are being used in different work packages, which makes comparison difficult and encourages compliance-oriented reporting instead of focused impact goals.
3. Policy impact is different and must be traced differently than other societal impact; each needs a framework to develop logic and adequate metrics.

What interview evidence adds

4. Stakeholder engagement can redirect research toward more usable outputs. One researcher described a policy brief as their most impactful publication because it reached investors, industry, media, and policymakers. However, incentives are misaligned: outputs with clear real-world reach and impact may still count little in tenure tracks.

³ Bruno, N., & Kadunc, M. (2019). Impact Pathways: Tracking and communicating the impact of the European Framework Programme for research and innovation. *fteval Journal for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation*(47), 62-71.

5. Noteworthy, project outputs with promising results often stall after funding ends because no other actor carries further research towards proof-of-concept or other TRL.

Lessons from the networks

6. Impact takes time. The most impactful networks reportedly ran for more than four years and combined realistic objectives and low personnel turnover, especially of key network managers.
7. Networks of people matter as much as networks of institutions. Stable relationships with ministries, farmers, and other stakeholders improve benefits' uptake.
8. Mandatory call requirements on co-production, Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), and other stakeholder engagements facilitate impact, particularly when they are supported by guidance and funding.

Implications for Horizon Europe and further framework programmes

9. Assessment should be rebuilt around a Theory of Change⁴, explicitly developing adequate KPIs, defining impact as beneficiaries of research outcomes.
10. Societal impact - identified in the study as the second-largest reported impact area after scientific impact- needs a dedicated framework built around scales of impact informing impact-tailored KPIs.
11. Policy impact should not be treated as just another societal impact category; it requires separate indicators focused on uptake, awareness, critical mass development, and strong science policy networks, among others.
12. Traceability of impact must continue after the end of programmes, since there is currently no formal mechanism to follow impact once a network ends. Networks are not capable of providing long-medium and long-term traceability. However, HEU Partnerships could plan follow up assessments.

Recommendations for research programme managers

13. Define impact clearly: Use a single operational definition anchored in beneficiaries of outcomes⁵, then specify separate pathways for scientific, societal, economic, and policy impacts.
14. Assess change, not just output; Replace or complement accountability indicators with evidence of contributions to behavioural, institutional, regulatory, or practice changes attributable to a network's work.

⁴ Mayne, J. (2017). Theory of change analysis: Building robust theories of change. *Canadian Journal of Program Evaluation*, 32(2), 155-173.

Quinn, R. E. C., Kim S.; (1988). *Paradox and transformation: Toward a theory of change in organization and management*. Ballinger Publishing Co/Harper & Row Publishers.

⁵ Reed, M. S. (2018). *The Research Impact Handbook* (2nd ed.). Fast Track Impact. <https://www.fasttrackimpact.com/product-page/the-research-impact-handbook-pdf>

15. Separate policy from societal impact; Develop dedicated policy impact indicators - for example citation in strategies, direct use by ministries, generating science-policy networks, or requests for follow-on advice, contributions establishing a discourse in policy process, etc.
16. Support post-project knowledge transfer; Create intermediary mechanisms or databases that connect researchers, public authorities, and market actors able to advance technologies and practices to higher readiness levels.
17. Secure long-term traceability; Plan - through REA, partnerships, or member states - for following outcomes after programme end so delayed impacts are not lost.
18. Implement top-down stakeholder engagements; Design calls with mandatory stakeholder engagement practices like RRI, co-creation, living labs or citizen science elements to promote a larger impact from individual projects.

GEH's experience suggests that impact assessment should move from counting deliverables to tracing how research networks influence decisions, institutions, policy, practices, economic and scientific activity, technology development, public opinion and science-policy-society interfaces over time.

The proposed framework for societal impact can be found in Appendix I.

3.6 Learnings from the Living Archive

Background

The GEH [Living Archive](#)⁶ aims to preserve best practices and managerial competences. A vast body of knowledge and experience has been collected in the GEH Initiatives from FP6 until today. To capitalise on that knowledge the Living Archive aimed to identify, develop and adapt best practice examples for use by current and future transnational R&I funding networks.

The archive gives access to a wide range of accessible documents across four thematic areas:

- Funding Modalities (how funding works)
- Widening & Outreach (inclusive engagement)
- Research Prioritisation (choosing focus areas)
- Monitoring, Evaluation & Impact Assessment (measuring impact)

Main learnings and suggestions

Produce short *know-how* documents alongside deliverables

The know-how that we have and newly generate is not captured in a usable format. This knowledge is contained in individual people and hidden in large reports that are often shared within a small circle of people. For new colleagues it is difficult to retrieve the actual process and required steps from those

⁶ Crosbie, B., Zuniga, E., (2026) *Living Archive of International Programming*, Green ERA-Hub, <https://www.greenerahub.eu/livingarchive>.

large documents. Deliverables describe what was done, but not how it can be repeated or adapted by future initiatives and leave out the practical part of the work. Additionally, people change careers and leave knowledge gaps that are difficult to fill. An easy and practical way to deal with this is to:

1. Add short know-how documents and templates
2. Summarize step by step what was done
3. Keep documents central and accessible and use platforms like Zenodo to keep documents accessible
4. Funding networks should collaborate in building an accessible knowledge base on joint programming activities to support their own and future activities.

Share how a network came to be on the networks site to support widening

Create a series of documents and tools to facilitate the participation of joint programming

New funding networks are formed after a long and often complicated process. It is for widening countries interesting to learn how this process works exactly. There is little guidance available at the moment on how organizations can become part of a joint programming initiative. Organisations from widening countries often lack clear guidance on how to engage with joint programming initiatives, including where to begin, whom to contact, and which activities or events can support participation.

Have examples online to learn from. Funding networks do take the initiative to reach out to widening countries, but it is often difficult to reach the right people at the right time. Therefore, it should be as easy and clear as possible for widening countries to reach out to us.

3.7 Learnings on Widening

Background

Widening participation and strengthening international collaboration are important elements of Joint Programming and European research and innovation cooperation. Within the Green ERA-Hub, WP6 focused on developing guidelines and recommendations to support widening activities in future joint initiatives both within and beyond Europe. The work aimed to strengthen collaboration with underrepresented countries and regions, support widening recommendations for future European Partnerships within the thematic scope of the GEH, and explore opportunities for institutional and project-level cooperation with non-EU countries. The work package focused on a stronger participation of the EU11 members, the western Balkan region, the Mediterranean region, African countries, and a global approach through collaboration with global initiatives. The results of this work have been published in Deliverable 6.1, Final guidelines for the outreach.⁷ Main learnings and suggestions on widening and opportunities for European Joint Programming activities are detailed below.

⁷ Hippolyte I. Deliverable 6.1 Final guidelines for the outreach. The Green ERA-Hub, 2025.

Main learnings and suggestions

“Innovation flourishes not only through funding or technology, but through alignment, trust, and shared purpose.”

The creation of an Inter-Partnership Task Force (IPTF) is proposed

The IPTF would serve as a strategic coordination network designed to act as the backbone of structured dialogue among diverse partnerships, including thematic and geographic partnerships. It would support the communication, exchange of data, and alignment across initiatives. A key function of such collaboration would be to support the co-creation of calls for proposals cross-cutting Partnerships, thereby supporting a cohesive and strategically integrated European research and innovation landscape and helping to avoid research gaps.

Bridge the gap between strategic research needs and existing instruments

The widening activities identified research themes that are either insufficiently addressed or entirely absent from current European funding mechanisms. It showed that many of these themes require a broader coalition of partners that both span regions and sectors to ensure that research outcomes are applicable and market ready. Specific attention is called towards:

1. Macro-regional logistics and infrastructure, with a focus on establishing sustainable and resilient food systems between East and West
2. Locally adapted innovations that include local conditions and community priorities, ensuring that project activities are adapted to regional contexts and need
3. Equitable partnerships between EU and non-EU countries, without systemic barriers to participation and knowledge exchange

A next generation of pan-continental partnerships can transcend traditional sectoral boundaries and embrace pan-continental themes that address pressing societal and environmental challenges. This includes new strategic research themes, social innovation and policy alignment, and data interoperability.

There is a need for a flexible, bottom-up, solution-oriented mechanism that enables co-construction and active engagement of participants

Such a mechanism would complement existing partnerships and address identified priority areas. It could operate in a similar way as the FP7-era ERA-Nets, using Coordination and Support Action schemes. These initiatives provided valuable flexibility and inclusiveness, especially for new or smaller participants, and should either be maintained or replaced with instruments offering comparable flexibility.

Implement maturation calls for the acceleration of innovation

Innovation without adoption is a missed opportunity. To bridge the gap between promising research and real-world impact, the introduction of maturation calls is proposed. These targeted instruments would support the transition of high-potential outputs into market-ready products, scalable services, or social innovations. Such calls could be complemented by a booster programme offering mentoring and

technical guidance, matchmaking between researchers and industry, support for regulatory readiness and user testing, translation of results into all EU languages to remove communication barriers, and strengthening of the science–policy and society interface.

In addition, engaging influential actors from academia, society, and industry can help amplify project results and support and the uptake of innovations by facilitating the transition from research to application.

Promote the participation of global initiatives such as the Global Research Alliance and the Belmont Forum in Horizon Europe partnerships

The Global Research Alliance on Agricultural Greenhouse Gases (GRA) brings countries together to find ways to grow more food without increasing greenhouse gas emissions. The Belmont Forum is a partnership of funding agencies, international scientific councils, and regional consortia dedicated to promoting transdisciplinary, transnational research to help understand, mitigate and adapt to global environmental change. Belmont Forum has already collaborated on several occasions with European programmes within the framework of Horizon2020. Both GRA and Belmont Forum are open to collaborate in joint initiatives that address topics within their respective scopes. This provides opportunities for the next generation of European Partnerships. Structural and procedural obstacles have been identified and the right processes need to be implemented to allow joint initiatives:

1. Platform interoperability and GDPR data transfer
2. Legal status and framework agreements
3. Alignment of call procedures and timelines
4. Joint topic selection and implementation
5. Eligibility criteria and interdisciplinarity requirements
6. Added value and incentives for participation.

3.8 Learnings on the support of Early Career Researchers

Background

The support of Early Career Researchers (ECRs) has been a major focus of the work carried out by WP7 in the Green ERA-Hub. The activities included study and work visits during which ECRs travelled for several weeks to a European research institute or public organisation, a summer school for ECRs, and two workshops aimed at supporting their networking and career-building skills.

Main learnings and suggestions

Early Career Researchers have a place in activities organised for researchers in the context of Joint Programming and international research consortia.

Early Career Researchers, such as PhD students and post-docs, are responsible for a substantial share of the work carried out in EU-funded projects. Yet, it is mostly the project coordinators who have the opportunity to represent their projects at meetings and, in doing so, learn from the international community and expand their networks. During the Joint Conference workshop (Berlin, 10–11 October 2024), ECRs working on projects funded by the GEH ERA-Nets provided specific feedback on their role in international research consortia. Having the opportunity to meet and work with researchers involved

in other funded projects and Joint Programming initiatives would support their professional development and create additional opportunities for learning and networking.

ECRs need practical career guidance and soft-skills training alongside their academic development.

Future Joint Programming initiatives and HEU projects should make ECR career development a core requirement. These projects should explicitly include training in soft skills and funding acquisition, rather than focusing solely on scientific output.

There are currently many opportunities for ECRs to develop scientifically, such as through poster sessions or initiatives that support field and laboratory work. However, the practical aspects of building a career are often neglected, even though they are equally important for those pursuing careers in academia or related fields.

Skills such as communicating effectively in international and intercultural environments, working in teams, and understanding different career pathways are essential, yet ECRs often lack guidance in these areas. During the summer school, we observed that sessions focused on these topics, such as building a strong CV, securing funding, and applying for fellowships, generated the highest levels of interest and engagement among the PhD students.

3.9 Learnings from Communication and Dissemination

Background

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation of the results are essential components of every transnational research and innovation (R&I) funding network. These activities increase the impact of the network and its funded projects while ensuring transparency in the operations and outputs of EU-funded initiatives. Lessons learned and successful practices from previously funded networks provide practical examples of how communication and dissemination activities can be made more effective and achieve wider outreach. These insights are gathered from the Communication Work Packages from the Green ERA-Hub and the ERA-Nets SusAn, SUSFOOD2, ICT-AGRI-FOOD and FOSC.

Main learnings and suggestions

Targeted time-intensive approaches to reach specific groups of stakeholders are an effective method to increase the impact of content or stakeholder participation, although they can be time-intensive.

The impact of the targeted approach is well seen in the Breakfast Club webinars that were given throughout the lifetime of the GEH. Individual webinars reached around 100 registrations each, resulting in roughly 60-70 participants. Consistent targeted promotion across LinkedIn, supported by direct email, proved effective. Short 30-second promotional videos were shared repeatedly on multiple LinkedIn pages, up to six times per day in the lead-up to webinars. Visibility increased significantly with frequency. Promotional materials were shared in online focus groups aligned with the upcoming webinar topic to reach the relevant audience. This helped to reach people who were already engaged and increased the level of participation. Additionally, a mailing list of past attendees was built for direct outreach with registration links for future sessions.

Overall, consistency was the biggest factor - regular visibility and repeated reminders made a significant difference in registrations.

Reaching a wider audience of stakeholders and the general public with communication and dissemination efforts requires a different approach with more resources and time, especially near the end of a network's lifecycle.

C&D activities of the GEH and ERA-Nets typically consist of building and maintaining a website with project pages, sharing newsletters and brochures, organizing live events and managing social media channels. Data analysis shows that websites are most actively visited during open calls for proposals and the launch of the project pages, afterwards the number of visitors decreases significantly. Newsletters and other materials are shared within a limited group and have lower click-through rates, events usually have a very specific group of stakeholders visiting.

Social media platforms are a useful vehicle to reach a much broader audience of stakeholders and the general public, especially near the end of the network's lifecycle when the funded projects have their research outcomes. However, the resources in a network are often depleted by that time. Weekly sharing of short informative messages (FOSC) typically reached tens to several thousand views per message. The level of actual interaction with the information remained, however, low. The experience from the Breakfast Club shows that a time-intensive and targeted approach is more successful in reaching a wider and more responsive audience. The same approach can be applied to increase the dissemination of project outcomes. This requires collaboration with project leaders to identify relevant stakeholder groups, gather interesting and relevant project information for online dissemination, and to allocate sufficient time and resources planned for the final stages of the network.

Visual materials such as videos and clips increase the outreach of news and results.

Videos showcasing projects and their results reached a larger group of people than regular news items and social media posts (SusAn, SUSFOOD2, FOSC). It proved to be an effective way to communicate project outputs, as the videos remain relevant for longer periods, can easily be reused in different contexts, and are well suited for repeated sharing across online platforms. Additionally, short promotional clips designed to spark interest and encourage engagement have been shown to be an effective way to share information and motivate a broader audience to register for events. (GEH Breakfast Club).

Valorisation products made by clustered research projects around shared topics produced new and exciting outputs with broader reach and higher visibility.

The ERA-Net FOSC had a positive experience with the dissemination of valorisation products developed by clustered projects. The network created opportunities for projects clustered around specific topics to combine their experiences and outputs and jointly develop additional valorisation products. These products included a manual, VR game, policy brief, and videos. The outreach of these products through social media channels was very positive, and the products remained available on several platforms, allowing them to be shared repeatedly over time.

Newsletters are an important means of informing stakeholders, but they generally reach a limited audience while requiring considerable time and effort to prepare. Efficient use of communication resources is therefore important.

Experience from preparing newsletters for the GEH and various ERA-Nets shows that a lot of time and effort is invested in producing informative, interesting, and visually strong newsletters. In the mentioned

ERA-Nets the number of subscribers reached up to a few hundred people and click-through rates remained relatively low. For communication offices it is therefore important to use time and resources efficiently when developing and planning newsletters, to consider how many newsletters to produce and how extensive they should be. The impact of newsletter content can be increased by reusing articles on project websites and by adapting and resharing content through social media channels.

3.10 Learnings provided by project researchers

Background

The workshop session '*Learning from the past*' at the Joint Conference in Berlin 10-11 October 2024 aimed to draw upon the knowledge and experience of 43 project researchers from 35 projects. Their input was used to learn how current and future networks can increase impact and bring projects further.

The 35 research projects were at various stages in their lifecycle, ranging from early-stage to completed projects, and covering topics in agriculture, food and biotechnology.

The various networks that funded these projects have organised several additional activities during the project runtime to support and to create synergy, such as conferences, trainings and workshops. The type and frequency of these activities differed per network. During this workshop session we discussed the effectiveness of those additional activities and what kind of additional activities would be beneficial for project impact, success and follow-up.

The session focused on understanding:

1. Which **network activities** (workshops, meetings, trainings, etc.) were particularly effective or appreciated by the researchers.
2. How the **impact of the projects** could have been **increased**, both during their duration and after their completion.
3. **What researchers need or would have needed** to advance their projects further. Including after project completion.
4. To define the **key learning points** for networks to improve project outcomes, in terms of effectiveness, impact, and efficiency.

The discussions took place in four break-out rooms. The outcomes of the discussions were remarkably similar, and several projects mentioned ideas and wishes that were successfully tried by other ERA-Nets. All groups mentioned the importance of the same topics:

- Communication support
- Stakeholder engagement
 - o Policy makers
 - o Industry
 - o Farmers
 - o General audience
- Support of Early Career Researchers

- Increased collaboration between projects
- Follow-up funding

Main learnings and suggestions

Effectiveness of organised activities for researchers

Researchers were very positive about the activities organised for them during the lifetime of the ERA-Nets. Especially the conferences and in-person trainings and workshops were considered valuable. The main reasons mentioned were the networking opportunities for future proposals, and the exchange with peers about research findings, new ideas and possibilities. Regarding the location of these events it was mentioned that accessibility should be taken into account, as some cities are more difficult to reach when traveling from certain countries. Additionally, it was mentioned in all break-out sessions that PhD students working on the various projects would like to have more opportunities to participate in these events.

Researchers who participated in workshops in which projects clustered around shared topics collaborated on valorisation activities were positive about both the collaboration itself and the impact of the resulting outputs, including videos, publications, and a virtual reality game.

Support that was given to Early Career Researchers was highly appreciated, such as an event targeted on Early Career Researchers and the Breakfast club seminars.

Ideas to increase impact of projects

Stakeholder engagement support

- Seminars focused on creating impact by connecting researchers with stakeholders
- Support in connecting with stakeholders from industry, and policymakers
- Co-create proposals with industry, or have a mentor from industry to increase the connection with the market
- Support and toolkits on citizen science
- Bridging the gap between solutions from research and regulations by connecting projects with experts on regulations and policymakers at national and EU level

Communication support

- Increased communication and dissemination from the networks Communication office
- Collaboration between projects on communication and dissemination activities
- Trainings on research communication
- Update the project pages on the network's websites more regularly
- Collaboration with multipliers such as artists and chefs

Support of Early Career Researchers

- Funding that allows PhD researchers to publish results, since projects usually end after three years
- Networking opportunities with balanced age groups
- Online webinar series focused on young researchers

Facilitate collaboration between projects

- Cluster projects around shared topics to create valorisation products and include budget for this specifically
- Additional networking and collaboration opportunities between projects funded by the same call

Follow-up funding

- Funding for higher TRL-level projects, follow-up projects and patent development

Other learnings

- Online network events in the proposal phase to foster new consortia and support researchers from widening countries
- More homogeneous national rules in the call would help the effectiveness of projects
- Inform about all required in-person meetings during the proposal phase and organize meetings back-to-back with regard to budgets

APPENDICES

Appendix I; Proposed framework for societal impact

Societal impact in the HE's Pathways to Impact is loosely defined and difficult to assess. Pathways like "Delivering impacts and benefits via R&I missions" or "Addressing EU policy priorities & global challenges through R&I" are difficult to conceptualize, assess and report in a consistent systematic manner, that allows for comparison across other societal impacts pathway implementations.

In order to ground the Societal Impact assessment, this study proposes a Framework for Societal Impact inspired by Reed (2018)⁸; and Reed et al. (2018)⁹ work on research impact. The purpose of the Framework is to list intended Policy and/or Societal Impacts and then implement a series of scales that help ground a realistic goal. This realistic goal informs the development of adequate KPIs for societal or policy impacts' assessments.

Below is the proposed framework for societal impact

Societal Impact Framework													
Type of intended societal impact	Stakeholders Scale	Geographical scale				Time scale		System scale *			Adoption scale **	KPIs Pathways to impact	
<i>Impact to policy</i>	<i>Stakeholders (in)directly benefited</i>	<i>Local</i>	<i>Regional</i>	<i>National</i>	<i>International</i>	<i><5 years</i>	<i>>5 years</i>	<i>Micro</i>	<i>Meso</i>	<i>Macro</i>		<i><5 years</i>	<i>>5 years</i>
Awareness and understanding of research in policy networks Attitudes and critical mass creation in publics Networking in science-policy-society interactions Knowledge Inputs for Public Policy Other impacts													
<i>Impact to society</i>													
Early adoptions in production practices Changes in relation to the environment Human living conditions & wellbeing Decision making in organizations Normative changes in society Knowledge transfer Other impacts													

* Micro = applied in production / applied research. Meso = scientific or academic / institutional knowledge / ERA network / research network. Macro = public policy / sector / research system / food system

** **Conceptual:** impact is only framed in theory or strategy. **Planned:** pathways, KPIs, or structures exist, but no convincing realised effects yet. **Early signal:** first indications of use or change, but evidence is still limited, local, or provisional (e.g. received policy briefs).

Adopted: there is clear evidence of use beyond the project team, for example by stakeholders, policy makers, networks, or organisations. **Commercialisation:** there is evidence of products, services, or tools reaching the user or market oriented development (TRL 4-9).

Institutionalised: impact is embedded in stable governance, public policy, coordination structures, recurring programmes, or policy-facing institutions.

⁸ Reed, M. S. (2018). *The Research Impact Handbook* (2nd ed.). Fast Track Impact. <https://www.fasttrackimpact.com/product-page/the-research-impact-handbook-pdf>

⁹ Reed, M. S., Bryce, R., & Machen, R. (2018). Pathways to policy impact: a new approach for planning and evidencing research impact [Article]. *Evidence & Policy*, 14(3), 431-458. <https://doi.org/10.1332/174426418x15326967547242>